

Abstract

This investigation explores the effect of 4 different music genres (classical, jazz, pop, rock) on long-term memory in adolescents ages 15-18. This study used an experimental design involving 50 students who listened to songs while memorizing a list of randomized letters within a given time limit. These students are then distracted and instructed to recall the list of randomized letters. The study's results are expected to contribute to further understanding of the relationship between music and cognition, especially in adolescents.

Introduction

Rationale

As the founder of my school's *Collaborative Learning* extracurricular club, I have been exploring ways to optimize learning for seniors. Amongst many factors, members of the club agreed that background music plays a large role in motivation and memorization. In this investigation, I will be exploring the optimal music genre. The genres I have chosen are among this experiment's findings and will be applied to my extracurricular club to enhance studying.

Recent studies suggest that 59% of students listen to music while studying (Sun et al.). There have been many studies focused on the general impact of music arousal on concentration, but there's a lack of research regarding music genres and their different effects. Prior research done by Sitong Chen shows evidence of a correlation between long-term memory and music genres (Chen 7) has inspired me to conduct my research using a bigger sample size to determine the most effective music genre to listen to while studying.

Background Information

Music is integral to human life, providing entertainment, emotion, and rich cultural experiences. However, in addition to these aspects, music can also affect cognitive functions, including short and long memory. Previous studies have shown that music can improve learning ability and information retention in children, adolescents, and adults.

This investigation encompasses the effect of music on two factors: overall mood & ability to memorize. The mood-arousal hypothesis states that, "changes in arousal and mood when exposed to auditory stimulation underlie the detrimental effects or improvements in cognitive performance." (Chee et al. 1) Furthermore, researchers at Harvard University claim that, "music seems to open doors to the residents' memory vaults" (Fabiny) when investigating the impact of music-arousal in patients of strokes or who have brain injuries. Music can trigger or be associated with emotional events, specific information, places, or people. This associative and contextual memory, stimulated by the hippocampus,

leads to the encoding and retrieval of memories (“The correlation between memory and music”). Music has been used in therapy for individuals suffering from Alzheimer’s disease and dementia as it stimulates memory circuits.

Although music is stimulating, music can be further classified into different genres which are determined by certain characteristics such as instruments, rhythmic patterns, tempo, lyrical content, etc. (“Music Genres”) Favourable characteristics that promote concentration and memory include slow tempo, lacking lyrics, and exhibiting a repetitive nature (“How Music Affects Memory and Concentration”). Therefore, music will not only boost concentration but also create associative memories that allow people to better recall stored information.

Hypothesis: I hypothesize that genres with less ambiance & lyrics, as well as and slower tempo, will stimulate concentration and improve memory better compared to genres with more lyrics and louder ambiance.

Methodology

Variables

Variable	Manipulation Technique(s)
<p>Independent Variables</p> <p>Music genre</p> <p>Classical - ‘Reverie’ by Debussy</p> <p>Jazz - ‘Misty’ by Laufey</p> <p>Pop - ‘Uptown Funk’ by Mark Ronson</p> <p>Rock - ‘Gimme Chocolate’ by BABYMETAL</p>	<p>In this exploration, 50 participants will be told to memorize 15 random letter combinations within 5 minutes while listening to the following songs. Songs will be played on a loop within 5 minutes.</p> <p>The same participants will undergo 3 trials, one for each song.</p>
<p>Dependent Variables</p> <p>1. Overall mood (Likert scale) & ability to memorize</p> <p>2. Number letter combinations recalled</p>	<p>1. Participants rank their overall ‘mood’ and ability to memorize on a Likert scale of 1-10.</p> <p>1 - Lowest overall mood & ability to memorize</p> <p>10 - Highest overall mood & ability to memorize</p> <p>2. Participants tick as many letter combinations as they can recall (15 out of 50)</p>

<p>Control Variables</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Time given for memorization, pause, and recalling 2. Volume of song 3. Access to memorization methods/ strategies 4. Distraction questions 5. Setting 6. Age 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Memorization time: 5 minutes Pause: 3 minutes Recalling: 5 minutes 2. The volume of each song is 50% 3. Participants are not given any materials (e.g. paper, writing utensils, gadgets) to memorize 4. Participants are given 50 different arithmetic questions as a distraction 5. Participants are placed in an empty room with only myself present for changing songs and providing the set of distraction questions 6. Age of participants involved are 15-17 years old
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Materials

1. 1 pair of Headphones
2. 1 Laptop
3. 1 Tablet
4. 1 Stopwatch
5. [List of randomly 15 random letter combinations](#)
6. [List of the full 50 random letter combinations](#)

(All random letter combinations are taken from <https://www.random.org/>)

List of songs:

1. Classical - 'Reverie' by Debussy
2. Jazz - 'Misty' by Laufey
3. Rock - 'Gimme Chocolate' by BABYMETAL
4. Pop - 'Uptown Funk' by Mark Ronson

Procedure

1. Participants are placed in an empty room and are given a pair of headphones
2. Participants are given an upside-down sheet of a randomly generated list of 15 random letter combinations
3. Participants are given 5 minutes to memorize the letter combinations while listening to 'Reverie'

4. After the memorization period, participants are required to solve as many arithmetic problems as possible within 3 minutes
5. Participants are shown a random letter combination and tick the combinations they have learned the combinations previously within 5 minutes

To avoid the order effect, half of the participants will listen in the order classical→jazz→pop→rock and the other half will listen in the order rock→pop→jazz→classical

Ethical Considerations

1. All participants are fully aware of the nature of the experiment before experimentation and consent to participate
2. Privacy and confidentiality of participant's identities as requested by the majority of the participants are ensured

Data Presentation

	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Average
Age (years)	3 years	15	18	16.93
Gender	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Average # of letter combinations correctly recalled	0.98	7.02	8.00	7.6
Overall Mood	1-10	1	10	7.13
Overall ability to memorize	1-10	1	10	6.22

Figure 1. Range and average of variables (correct to 2 decimal points)

	Average # of letter combinations correctly recalled			
Genre of music	Classical	Jazz	Pop	Rock
	7.50	7.88	8.00	7.02

Figure 2. Average # of letter combinations correctly recalled (correct to 3 significant figures)

Genre of music	Average ranking of mood and ability to memorize (Likert scale 1-10)			
	Classical	Jazz	Pop	Rock
Overall Mood	8.00	7.25	8.50	4.75
Overall Ability to Memorize	7.02	6.50	6.10	5.25

Figure 3. Average ranking of mood and ability to memorize (Likert scale 1-10) (correct to 2 decimal points)

Data Analysis & Discussion

According to the data above, there is a trend between each genre and overall mood & overall ability to memorize. The order from least to most beneficial song genres (on average) according to:

1. Average # of letter combinations correctly recalled:
Pop, Jazz, Classical, Rock
2. Overall mood:
Pop, Classical, Jazz, Rock
3. Overall ability to memorize:
Classical, Jazz, Pop, Rock

There are variations between the trends of each variable investigated in this paper.

Firstly I will discuss the trend associated with the average # of letter combinations correctly recalled. It can be concluded that out of the 50 participants ages 15-18, the most efficient genre of music is Pop (8.00 / 15), followed by Jazz. Similarly, Pop ranked the highest in terms of overall mood (8.5 / 10), followed by Classical. Lastly, Classical ranked highest in the overall ability to memorize (7.02 / 10). Contrastingly, Classical ranked third in terms of letter combinations correctly recalled, one possible explanation for its higher ranking in overall mood and overall ability to memorize is the Placebo Effect as some participants might be under the impression that Classical music can induce better effects on long-term memorization.

Amongst all categories, Pop is proven to be most effective in terms of memory and psychology. An experiment conducted by Macquarie University Professor William Forde Thompson supports this argument as he claims that uplifting music, “has the ability to put us in a better mood, which therefore increases our IQ. (Hernberg)” Therefore, it can be stated that the upbeat, lightheartedness of pop music can uplift the participants’ moods, thereby increasing their IQ and ability to memorize. On the other hand,

Rock ranked last and when participants were asked why this was, they claimed that the genre was too distressing and caused irritability instead of the intended effect of improving memory.

Conclusion

According to my findings, my hypothesis that “genres with less ambiance & lyrics, as well as a slower tempo, will stimulate concentration and improve memory better compared to genres with more lyrics and louder ambiance,” is proven false. My findings show a negative correlation between increasingly ambient music and memorization. However, the ability to memorize is not solely dependent on background music, hence the results could be another underlying factor. In addition, my findings also provide evidence of improved overall mood and ability to memorize, suggesting that more uplifting music (Pop) induces a better psychological response and approach to learning compared to distressing and noisy background music (Rock). To conclude, Pop background music is recommended not only for increased ability to store long-term information, but to increase mood while studying.

Works Cited

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